

An Exploration of the Downfall of Jute Industry with Perspective of Knowledge Management: A Case Study of Sindh, Pakistan

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Abstract

This qualitative research explores the factors behind the downfall of the jute industry in Pakistan, specifically in region of Sindh. Through preliminary informal interviews, a major cause of downfall is identified which is the lack of formal knowledge management mechanism within the firms and industry. Accordingly, a knowledge transfer mechanism is proposed for the efficacy of knowledge transfer in the firms and hence improves the overall knowledge management of the industry which is later validated through formal interviews with industry experts. The literature states that in Pakistani context there is a dearth of awareness of the proper knowledge transfer in SMEs. For this research, to fulfill the aim of exploration of the factors behind, a collapsed jute firm is taken into consideration in the Sindh region of Pakistan as a case study. Therefore, to ascertain reasons of the downfall of the industry, semi-structured interviews were conducted from 11 personnel from industry and academia and were analyzed by using the manifest qualitative content analysis technique to identify the underlying rationales and gap between the connected entities. The findings suggests that, there are many veiled factors behind the downfall of the prosperous firm, amongst those is the lack of government support, since Pakistan is the jute dependent country, so in such environment the unit setups look forward for the helping hand from the government. Additionally, it was also found that in Pakistani context there is no any practice of succession planning in the firms of any type, leading to many unspoken problems. One of such problem is absence of codification, which in turn makes difficult for the firms to transfer the knowledge to the coming generations. It was also observed that, the industrial units are always looking forward to have a collaborative link to the knowledge generating units known as universities. Likewise the academia is also intended to approach to have such linkages to the industries to create a more developed milieu. On the whole this study is an attempt to comprehend the significance of knowledge transfer as one of the factor in understanding the downfall of the firm and to look for the ways with which the knowledge management of the industry can be developed.

Keywords: Knowledge transfer, Knowledge Management, Jute industry, Succession Planning, Sindh, Pakistan.

1. INTRODUCTION

There are many factors which can help organizations to achieve competitive advantage and hence progress in their performance (Susanty et al., 2012). Nowadays, many organizations in Pakistan are facing complex and continuous changing environment. Jute industry is one such industry in Pakistan which have lost its significance in both the agriculture and hence in the market. The world is going green today, almost all the production and packaging industries are switching their choices to the sustainable option of making the environment less pollutant, and choosing jute in the packaging their products. Jute is the natural fiber which in its structure is long, shiny and soft. It is twirled into coarse long threads. Jute is one of the most affordable natural fibers in existence and it is second only to cotton in amount produced and variety of uses. It is also the most important natural fiber after cotton in terms of cultivation and usage. The jute fibers are mainly composed of plant materials cellulose and lignin. The industrial term used for jute fiber is raw jute. Jute is the crop that helps to keep environment clean as it requires less fertilizer. At present, Pakistan has 5 active jute mills, out of which two Amin fabric ltd and Indus jute mills ltd are in province Sindh. Their overall

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contribution is moderate, because of the fact that Amin fabric ltd is facing an existential threat to survive in the market. A declining industry is characterized as an industry where growth is either negative or is not growing at the large rate of economic growth and monetary development. There is plethora of possible rationales behind a weakening of the industry: for instance, consumer demand may be gradually evaporated, the depletion of a natural resource might be occurring or there can be the emergent alternates because of technological innovation. An industry is understood to be in a decline phase, when it is not able keep pace with the rest of the country's economic growth .Jute industry in Pakistan is also at the verge of its decline and the most major reasons behind are competition from the polypropylene, lack of raw jute, constant power crisis, lack of knowledge management and transfer etc. Knowledge management is the methodical process that maintains the continuous development of individual group and organization learning and involves creation, acquisition, gathering, transmission transfer, and appliance of knowledge to achieve organizational objectives. Knowledge management in context of Pakistani industries has becoming a point of concern for many industrialists and researchers, because knowledge-intensive industries cannot risk on losing the knowledge. Thus this impact of knowledge loss can be mitigated through knowledge management. Results of different studies have indicated that industries in Pakistan have absence of knowledge management as a strategic response to knowledge loss.(Hassan, 2014)

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Knowledge Defined

According to Becerra-Fernandez I, Sabherwal R. (2010), knowledge is a deliberate structure of facts, relationships, experience, skills and insights that generate action. In addition, Sensuse (2014) stated that knowledge is an important skill for company progress. It is embodied within the company and should process through the social interchange. The quality of the work does not only depend upon the ability to generate, give out and share knowledge but rather how the knowledge is used in the company (Pasaribu et al, 2017). In organizations, it often becomes embedded not only in documents or store but also in organizational routines, processes, practices, and norms (Davenport and Prusak, 1998).

2.2 Knowledge Transfer

Knowledge transfer has no single definition, which is accepted by wide groups of scientists. However, a definition given by Argote and Ingram is used by a lot of other researchers. They describe organizational knowledge transfer as “the process through which one unit (e.g. group, department, or division) is affected by the experience of another.”(Argote and Ingram, 2000, p.151). Conversely, the following explanation is possible: “Knowledge transfer is understood as a process in which an organization recreates and maintains a complex, causally vague set of routines in a new setting” (Szulanski, 2000, p. 10). As far as diverse literature is available on the definition of Knowledge, it is not firmly defined. Other than this reality, one thing is significant that in whatever form or dimension knowledge is existing, it must be kept effectively flowing from person to person within the organization, and within the region, so as to develop the collaboration of the firms (local buzz).The term local buzz was introduced and defined by Bathelt et. al (2004).. Knowledge transfer in firms can be defined as the process through which one unit (e.g.; group, section or division) is influenced by the experience of another. This definition of knowledge transfer is analogous to definitions of transfer at the individual level of analysis in cognitive psychology. Even if the knowledge transfer in firms involve transfer at the individual level, the problem of knowledge transfer rise above the individual dimension to group, product line, department or division. Therefore, knowledge transfer can be measured either by changes in knowledge or by changes in the performance. This measurement of knowledge transfer may pose to some challenges. Nonaka (1991) states that an important part of the knowledge that firms acquires may be tacit knowledge which is not easy to articulate. Tacit knowledge may be defined as that kind of knowledge that is difficult to transfer by one person to another by means of writing it or verbalizing it, because it is a set or store of unwritten, unspoken knowledge that is practically held by every human being.

2.3 Knowledge Transfer in Human Resource Management

The significance of knowledge transfer in human resource management is widely recognized. This is one of the possible reasons why some organizations perform better than other. Human resource management is

responsible for the overall management of the organizational workforce. This includes recruitment selection and introduction, personnel administration, training and development, performance and reward management, talent management, succession and career planning, labor relation, human resource planning. According to (Ukertot, 2013), HRM is termed to be universal in context of strategies, policies and processes. The most major role of the management in knowledge transfer is to make sure that it has the intellectual capital which is required by the firm (Wambui, 2013). Armstrong in (2006) and Aziri et al (2013) emphasize that it is the role of the human resource management to make sure that right knowledge should lead to the organizational performance. It is the duty of HR to help in developing an open culture in which trends should be set to accentuate the significance of knowledge sharing, to create and promote an environment of dedication and trust, to guide the workforce to design such groups which can facilitate knowledge transfer through networks, and then to motivate and reward people who do so. It is the responsibility of the managers to organize such seminars, workshops, conferences and symposia which can assist the knowledge transfer from one person to another. Valentine (2011) identify that through the development of right knowledge system the organizations progress in their work practices, will be able to take improved decisions, and will know the best way to steer themselves away from the criticism that hinder them to learn from the previous experiences. In the innovative culture, the employees feel free to learn from the mistakes, they can openly propose their thought and ideas for the betterment of the firm. Such a culture gives them sense of belongingness. In such a scenario, tools are created which appreciate the creation; sharing and transferring of tacit knowledge in organization (Wambui, 2013). Some researchers also say that effective knowledge transfer help to identify the stock of tacit knowledge in the firm, and then the tacit knowledge can be codified to explicit knowledge.

2.4 Knowledge Transfer Mechanisms

Knowledge transfer is defined as the sharing and circulation of knowledge in such a way that it can be used successfully to solve problems. In organizational theory the knowledge transfer is a practical problem of transferring knowledge from one part of an organization to another. Oxford dictionary defines word mechanism as “a method or a system of achieving something”. Thus knowledge transfer mechanism can be defined as the process or system in which knowledge is created, organized, stored and distributed in such a way that it becomes available for everyone in the future and is useful to solve related problems”.

2.5 Effective Knowledge Transfer

It is evident from the practices of the successful firms that effective knowledge transfer can lead to sustainable growth. Many authors like (Lucas, 2010; Robu, Lazar, & Brady-Fryer, 2015; Rottman, 2008; Venkitachalam & Bosua, 2014) have explained the importance of an effective knowledge transfer with knowledge perspective, that a trusting and an open organizational culture is necessary for the success of the organization. Likewise, (Afzal & Afzal, 2014; Zack, 1999; Suzanne Zyngier & Burstein, 2012) agree that it is a must to add the correct information system as well as a supporting infrastructure in developing an effective knowledge transfer mechanism. A similar study was conducted in Norway in 2016 by Alessia et al., which showed the relationship between effective knowledge transfer and successful partnering projects in the perspective of construction industry. The study showed that, partnering factors like cooperation, mutual trust, and open communication are directly related to successful knowledge transfer. With this perspective in support of knowledge, it is very much clear from the findings of many authors, that an effective knowledge transfer mechanism has one of the founding positions in the achievement of goal of an organization.

2.6 Knowledge Transfer in Successful Family Firms

Many domestic firms in Pakistan are the family business oriented firms. Also the case study considered for this study i.e. the jute industry of Sindh, mainly are family businesses. The main and the most critical change that the family business deals with is the succession process i.e. the replacement of the key personnel. This phenomenon is a natural process to happen, but it is also the most difficult period in lives of the families and the employees of the firms, because in handing over the business to the next generation the founder dreams

to pass on the trust of its potential clients and the reputation that the firm has earned. According to Handler (1992), in evaluating the succession process two targets are sought: quality and effectiveness. Quality is defined as the indication of how the involved family members personally experience the process, whereas the effectiveness is more of the concerned to how others evaluate the result of the succession. In order to achieve this quality-effectiveness standards (Varamäki, Pihkala, and Routamaa, 2003) suggested that there are three vital elements that must be transferred between the generations, which are:

1) Ownership /power,2) Management responsibility ,and 3) Competence /knowledge. Focusing on the third element, Rosa et al. (2010) developed a model “Knowledge Transfer Model in Family Firms (KTFF)”which enlightens the conditions and variables under which the effective inter-generational knowledge transfer takes place.

2.7 Knowledge Transfer in SMEs

We call SMEs, as small and medium-extent enterprises, having various interpretations internationally purely based upon specific economic umbrella of the operations. It is purely based on the businesses operations all around the world. Usually, SMEs is a generic identification of any sovereign firm having >50. In US terms it is defined as an enterprise >500 workers. (Corporate finance institute, 2019)⁵.The description of SMEs differ from country to country on the basis of few limited criteria such as number of employees, values of assets, sales and volume of output (Cunningham & Rowley, 2008), and this is same here in Pakistan also (Dasanayaka, 2008;Mustafa &Khan,2005;Rana, Khan& Asad, 2007).The Small and Medium Enterprise bank (SME Bank), Small and Medium Enterprises Development Authority (SMEDA),Pakistan Bureau of Statistics (PBS) and State Bank of Pakistan (SBP) have described SMEs in different ways(Dar, Ahmed, & Raziq, 2017); such as SMEDA, defines an SME upon the number of employees and total number of productive assets .The SME bank uses only total number of assets as the criterion. PBS has the criterion of the number of employees. Whereas, SBP’s definition of a SME is created keeping in view multiple characteristics, such as: the nature of the business, number of employees, amount of capital employed and annual net sales value. Internationally the researchers are keen to the subject of knowledge transfer and progress of SMEs, as to establish the source and understand the link between both Knowledge Transfer and Subjective Progress of given SME. Kaminski et al, in 2008anticipated the importance of shared knowledge and technological capabilities in developing new products .Internationally and Regionally, the trade organizations and other allied institutions are letting more weightage and activating link in creation and establishment of SMEs on the basis of transfer of knowledge to small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and the effectiveness of this knowledge transfer.(Kerste & Muizer,2002).In this era we are facing with more advanced and developed form of industries than ever before. Progress and development have started the increasingly fierce competition, and hence given rise to problems for some SMEs. One of such problems is faced by SMEs in Indonesia that is lacking or having some difficulties on knowledge transfer (Rumanti, Hidayat, & Saputro, 2016). Butel et,al in 2009 also emphasized on the significance of knowledge sharing and IT technology in Turkish SMEs, where most of the Turkish textile and apparel industry run as a family business and they mostly rely upon old technology and are very much reluctant to adopt change of any kind. In such a condition the owners and the managers are not ready and do not consider that how much important it is to transfer knowledge to be successful. In doing so they not only prevent the outflow of knowledge but also put barriers in acquiring knowledge from outside consequently making knowledge transfer activities even harder.

3 Clusters And Knowledge Framework

The framework proposed by Bathelt et.al (2004) elaborates the dynamics and the structure of knowledge creation in a defined geographical region known as cluster. The paper aims to propose how knowledg is created within the firms and how it is exchanged within them consequently how global pipelines are formed. The well-known framework is given below:

⁵ An online institute

Figure 1: The Structure and Dynamics of Local Buzz and Global Pipelines

4 Conceptual Framework

This research study incorporates the concept of knowledge creation in a firm, along with the external sources of knowledge; which act as triggers to stimulate growth in a firm and a region. Knowledge management is defined as an integral process of creating, sharing, using and managing the knowledge. The research conceptual framework is presented in figure 1, which explains the concept of knowledge transfer within firm and its impact on the knowledge management of the whole industry. The research conceptual framework considers absorptive capacity of firm as an originator for the transfer, with antecedent factors that affect the absorptive capacity of the firms. Moreover, the link between the knowledge transfer within firm and knowledge management of the industry is fortified with moderating variables. The conceptual framework as shown in figure 2 along with the linkages of variables is discussed thoroughly in following section.

*In house R&D, Technology and Innovation, Organizational Culture, Prior Knowledge, External Knowledge Sources

**Shared Experience, Social Relation, Common Language, Geographical Distance

Figure 2: Conceptual framework of knowledge transfer mechanism in firm with reference to knowledge management.

Source: Self-compilation and adopted from Cohen and Levinthal (1990) and Bathelt et.al (2004).

3.1 Description of the Variables and Links

This research adopts the concepts of knowledge creation in local region from Bathelt et al. (2004), while the concept of absorptive capacity has been widely discussed and adopted by many researchers. The term absorptive capacity as mentioned earlier was first suggested by Cohen and Levinthal in 1990 since then this term has been constantly used by different scholars to argue and present their opinions with respect to their concerning determinants of interest. This research study, accepts to consider absorptive capacity as an originator of the framework, where it is suggested to be the most essential constituent of the firm when knowledge comes in. Absorptive capacity is the independent variable for the research, which influence the knowledge management of the industry. Moreover, absorptive capacity holds some antecedent factors which are in house R&D, Technology and innovation, organizational culture, prior knowledge, external knowledge sources that are put forward in this framework according to the socio-economic conditions of sample of the study. Knowledge management is implied as the dependent variable. The influence of independent variable over dependent variable is carried forward through a mediating variable, which causes mediation in between. Here, knowledge transfer within the firm acts as the mediating variable among the absorptive capacity and knowledge management. In addition to this, the relationship between the mediating variable and dependent variable is reinforced by some social factors that play in as moderating variable for the framework. Those factors are: shared experience, social relation, common language and geographical distance. This complete process is said to have an effect, called as moderated mediation; where the variation effect of the independent variable (absorptive capacity) on the dependent variable (knowledge management of industry) via a mediating variable (knowledge transfer within firm) differs depending on the intensity of a moderating variable(social factors).

Absorptive Capacity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The ability to acquire new external knowledge, assimilate or transform the knowledge into usable form then to apply it to business ends or what we say at its commercial end. • Absorptive capacity covers an organization's aptitude to achieve competitive advantage by valuing; recognizing, acquiring and exploiting new external knowledge.
Antecedent Determinants of Absorptive Capacity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In-House R & D acts as a facilitator that generates new knowledge, enhances the learning practice of the individual and firms, invent and create new information, absorb technological solution and recognize new needs for knowledge. • Technology & Innovation can be defined as the ability of the firm to assimilate imported technology, depending on their organizational technological capabilities. • External Knowledge is created outside the boundary or firm; it is a combination of new resources, ideas, technologies, learning from partners, suppliers, customers, competitors and consultants that support the innovation and knowledge management process of the firm. • Organizational Culture determines values and beliefs which are an integral part of what one opt to see and absorb (Davenport & Prusak 2000). • Prior Knowledge is the previous knowledge that the learner already has before getting new knowledge or information.
Moderating Variables	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shared Experiences helps to identify individuals that have same culture, city, profession, organization, team, super culture or sub culture and interest. It helps to build a trust worthy and problem solving team that generate and responsible to create new knowledge within the firm. • Social Relation is interaction between two or more individuals. Researchers have suggested that close social relationships are associated with a number of positive outcomes such as happiness, less stress, engaged more in work and work related issues etc.(Hughes, 2001). • Common Language is a method of human communication and considered as precursor to transfer processes. It also enhances communication and exchanges in general. • Geographical Distances potentially damage the knowledge relationships, by decaying the loss of knowledge and trust which consequently weaken the ability of the firm to act at and over distance (Goodall and Roberts, 2003).

4. OBJECTIVES

1. To identify the dormant potential of jute industry by taking into accounts the historical perspective.
2. To investigate the past knowledge transfer mechanisms displayed by the small and medium firms to explore their limitations.

3. To propose a framework through the lens of the seminal work of “Clusters and Knowledge: Local buzz, Global Pipelines and the Process of Knowledge Creation” by Bathelt et al., (2004).

5. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND DATA SOURCES

This research study is exploratory and deductive in nature. As the name implies that these types of research is carried out for the exploration or investigation of research question. The target population for this research study is the jute firms of Pakistan and the sample drawn from the population is the jute firms of Sindh province. The collection of data is guided by the conceptual framework, which focuses on interacting dependent and independent variables. Two types of data (i.e. primary and secondary) were collected to get the answer of all three research objectives. After the data collection completed, the compilation and transcribing takes places and analyze the data through content analysis as shown in figure 2.

Figure 3: Research Methodology

5.1 Data Collection Technique and Sources

i) Primary data

The collection of primary data was done through formal, face-to-face semi-structured and open-ended interviews from the targeted population. The sample of the population includes the owner, managers and employees of the jute firms of Sindh. It also includes the business personnel and firms owners of SMEs. For the collection of data, the non-probability sampling technique is used. Non-probability sampling technique has five types i.e. i) quota sampling ii) convenience sampling iii) purposive sampling iv) self-selection sampling and v) snowballing sampling. To achieve the research objectives 1 and 3 the data collection tool was the semi-structured interviews. These 5 face-to-face semi-structured interviews were taken from the personnel of the firms; data is gathered through purposive sampling⁶ technique while for research objective 2 snowballing⁷ technique is used.

ii) Secondary data

The secondary data is collected from the sources like newspapers, government reports, PJMA annual reports, media articles, literature review, archives, and websites.

5.2 Data Analyses Tool and Technique

The qualitative data analysis is initiated by the transcription of the acquired data. This study employs content analysis technique to interpret, understand and analyze the gathered data. Content analysis is a technique that is used to make replicable and valid conclusions by interpreting and coding textual material. These materials may include documents, oral communication and graphics. Since the main source of data for this research study is the interviews, hence the gathered data is transcribed and analyzed. Content analysis has two types i.e. latent and manifest. This research study best describe through manifest content analysis because it is done for the purpose of investigation. In manifest content analysis the interpretation is taken from as the words are spoken by the respondent. The researcher describes what the informant or interviewer is actually saying. The process of content analysis includes coding, sorting, sifting and theme formation. Following the process, themes were developed. For instance the themes for objective no:1 were: non-supportive role of government, dependency and inadequacy of raw jute, achievements and recognitions, an attempt of jute farming ,present local and global potential of jute industry.

6. RESULTS

The results showed up many factors that play equal role in the downfall of the firm. Many factors are a part of the social set up and others are implicated in the internal system. To comprehend the first objective factors like, non-supportive role of government, dependency and inadequacy of raw jute, achievements and recognitions of the industry, an attempt of jute farming and present local and global potential of jute industry were highlighted. For second objective determinants like unclear status of succession planning, differing attitudes towards knowledge, lack of trust, influencing factor of knowledge transfer in industrial setup, absence of codification, contribution of cultural crisis and requirement of academia intervention were affirmed. The last objective of the study demonstrates the factors: nature of relationship between academia and industry, position of industry, university intervention as requisite, collaborative step and cultural complexity. In addition, the framework that was composed by the researcher, through the opinion, critical viewpoint and recommendation of the respondents was updated and a path of feedback was added to it. The reorganized framework is given in the figure no: 4.

*In house R&D, Technology and Innovation, Organizational Culture, Prior Knowledge, External Knowledge Sources

**Shared Experience, Social Relation, Common Language, Geographical Distance

Figure 4: Conceptual framework of knowledge transfer mechanism in firm with reference to knowledge management with feedback.

Source: Self-compilation and adopted from Cohen and Levinthal (1990) and Bathelt et.al (2004).

7. CONCLUSION

This study finding is based on exploratory and deductive attempt to look into the deeper reasons behind the downfall of an industry. It was observed that, there are different factors which originate the exploitation of the actual role and significance of the knowledge management and its components. The historical review of the industry shows the lack of interest and limited support by the government. Comparing the past and the present circumstances of the industry, it can be concluded that it is of prime importance to reach out for help of the dying firm and make it place in parallel to the one that is striving to fulfill the demand, doing so will improve the social, financial conditions and livelihood of the communities in that region. The risk of leaving any industry unattended and non- operating can leave a long term, irreversible loss, as the industry is overlooked by the concerned groups. This research study also concluded that the knowledge transfer mechanism of the SMEs were weak and faced absence of a distinctly agreed factor i.e. inconstant system of knowledge transfer in firms whether it be a family oriented business firm or small SME. Moreover, it was also found that the firms in the observed context of study were extremely lacking the practice of codification. In addition to that, differing mind-sets were monitored regarding the acceptance of the knowledge from various sources and an intense sense of distrust was observed leading to an unfaithful environment for people who want to put in for the prosperity of the firm. Along with the internal issues some external issues of huge significance were also unwrapped that are in actual a part of the cultural roots and are continuously weakening the social set up. Some of those issues can be managed by proper handling of the government, banning of the unions and associations is one of them. Taking further, the codification of the firms strictly requires an intervention by knowledge generating units, which can help the fresh scholars to get hands on experience, making them of more worth for the industry. Similar steps can be taken by the industries by granting scholarships and other financial assistance for the students. This two way act can reinforce the actual worth of research, which will benefit both the academia and the industries to answer the real problems. During the critical examination of the factors behind along with the viewpoints gathered, it came to discern that in Pakistan there are all kinds of institutes (i.e. research and development, supportive institute, technical institute and academia, jute mill association, small and medium enterprises association etc) are present, but there isn't any empowerment to them. The research study contributes by proposing a framework for the betterment of the knowledge transfer within the firms and its impact on the overall industry. Proper knowledge transfer within the firms can create self-sustaining vicinity for the firms to grow.

8. RECOMMENDATION

For the purpose of the affluence and success of the firms in the context of Pakistan, there is a dearth of understanding of the importance of effective knowledge transfer mechanism within the firm and its impact on overall industry. Therefore, for this purpose academia is considered as a point of elevation to create a collaborative shift in between. To overcome the gap, such policies can be made mandatory that can assist both the sides to fulfill their own demands and to alleviate the problems. The academia should create a ground for the awareness of the understanding of the basic problems of industries on the technical, managerial and operational grounds.

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